

Enhancing timing of Ce-doped garnet scintillators by complex codoping

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Abstract— The paper focuses on the methods to enhance timing resolution of Ce-doped garnets by aliovalent cooping to meet the requirement of new high energy physics experiments at colliders. Combined $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ doping of YAG:Ce and GAGG:Ce hosts provides an enhanced scintillation parameters, namely a light yield of 21600 phot/MeV, decay time of 26.4 ns, and CTR of 132 ps FWHM that meet the specified requirements. While GAGG host seems more promising to provide fast timing due to high segregation coefficient of Ce, YAG, as well as other Ga-free hosts are more promising from the point of crystal cost as they can be obtained in cheap W and Mo crucibles. Another promising direction of Ga-free garnets is Sc-codoped YAG:Ce crystals with varying Sc content, which were also grown in W crucibles. The accelerated decay time of 21 ns was achieved in YAG:Ce,Sc,Ca at the light yield of ca. 11000 ph/MeV.

Index Terms—Crystal Growth, Large Hadron Collider, Garnets, Luminescence, Scintillators

I. INTRODUCTION

THE choice of scintillation materials, especially for applications like TOF-PET or future collider T experiments, heavily depends on their timing characteristics. While cerium-activated oxide scintillation single crystals are known for their fast performance due to rapid d-f relaxation in Ce^{3+} , the extended scintillation decay time of GAGG:Ce, the brightest oxide scintillator, falls short of meeting the requirements of certain experiments, such as the upgrade 2 of the central part of the electromagnetic calorimeter of LHCb experiment [1]. Additionally, GAGG:Ce and other Ga-containing scintillators are typically grown in large sizes exclusively in Ir crucibles. Attempts to substitute Ga with Sc in the gadolinium garnet (GSAG:Ce,Mg) grown from Mo crucibles resulted in a significant decrease in light yield compared to GAGG:Ce without a notable improvement in timing [2].

The use of Ce-doped garnets in high-rate scenarios faces challenges due to the prolonged radiation lifetime of Ce^{3+} within these hosts. Efforts to reduce scintillation rise/decay times mainly rely on codoping with divalent alkali metals, typically Mg^{2+} , to facilitate partial Ce^{3+} transfer to Ce^{4+} and mitigate carrier trapping. However, this often leads to a substantial decrease in light yield due to the thermal ionization of electrons

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from Ce^{4+} excited levels to the conduction band [3]. Meanwhile, recent investigations into the divalent codoping of $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ (YAG:Ce) have shown promising results, with Ca^{2+} effectively eliminating slow components while the main decay time remains relatively slow at 55 ns [4]. A significant decrease in scintillation decay time is necessary while the light yield should be at least 10000-15000 phot/MeV.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

Crystals were grown by the Czochralski method using induction heating furnaces. The growth process was carried out using tungsten crucibles, carbon insulation in Ar + CO atmosphere. The crystals with a diameter of 10–15 mm and cylinder height of 60–70 mm were pulled from melt with a rate of 1–2 mm/hour and rotation rate of 10 rpm with automated diameter control by a weight sensor. The samples of $5 \times 5 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ and $5 \times 5 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$ dimensions were cut and polished for tests of optical and scintillation properties.

Scintillation decay time spectra were measured with Hamamatsu R6231 PMT excited with 662 keV γ -rays from ^{137}Cs source. Signal from PMT anode was fed to the input of Rigol DS6064 19 oscilloscope. Scintillation decay was approximated by the sum of two to three exponentials.

The light output of the first batch of samples (Fig. 2.12a) was measured with a PMT under 662 keV excitation (with Rhodorsil grease coupling and Teflon wrapping to maximize light collection). The time coincidence resolution of some $2 \times 2 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ samples were measured at CERN with dedicated setup exploiting NINO board for SiPMs readout.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study focuses on the double codoping of YAG:Ce with Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} cations. A similar approach was recently proposed for GAGG:Ce ceramics, resulting in an effective decay time (τ_{eff}) of 38 ns and a high light yield of 27400 ph/MeV [5], albeit without optimized doping concentrations. With finely tuned dopant concentrations, YAG:Ce,Ca,Mg achieves a better decay time to light yield ratio compared to present GAGG:Ce,Mg crystals, with a light yield of 21600 ph/MeV and rise/decay times of 30 ps/26 ns, respectively. The synergistic effect of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} codopants is discussed, leading to enhanced timing parameters while maintaining a high light yield.

Furthermore, YAG:Ce,Mg,Ca crystals were successfully grown in this study using the Czochralski method with inexpensive W crucibles, offering a cost-effective alternative to Ga-containing crystals grown in large sizes exclusively in Ir crucibles. Therefore, this approach presents an appealing alternative to GAGG:Ce-based scintillators for fast-timing applications [6].

Fig. 1. YAG:Ce,Sc, crystals with varying Sc content irradiated by UV-light.

In parallel, an attempt was made to reduce the luminescence decay time in YAG:Ce crystals by adding Sc that modifies the band gap by analogy with Ga addition into GAGG:Ce, and Ca^{2+} , which induces transfer of cerium Ce^{3+} to Ce^{4+} and eliminates carrier trapping. $(\text{Y}_{1-x-y}\text{Ce}_x\text{Ca}_y)_3(\text{Al}_{1-z}\text{Sc}_z)_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG:Sc,Ce,Ca) crystals with a Sc content of up to 25 at.%, were grown (Fig. 1). Polished crystalline elements were annealed in oxidizing atmosphere. Optical absorption spectra clearly indicate the partial transfer of Ce into tetravalent state. The main Ce^{3+} band at 460 nm band remarkably weakened, while the short-wavelength (<300 nm) absorption increased, which corresponds to the $\text{Ce}^{4+} - \text{O}^{2-}$ charge transfer absorption, as well as may certify the reduction in the band gap. The maximum light yield of 14600 ph./MeV with an averaged luminescence decay time of 21.2 ns corresponds to 1 at. % Sc-doped sample. Further increase of Sc concentration in YAG:Sc,Ce,Ca leads to reduction in the decay time, but even faster decrease in the light yield (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Scintillation parameters of the obtained crystals in comparison with state-of-the-art counterparts.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results certify that parameters of Ce-doped YAG and GAGG are similar at proper $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ codoping, which eliminates carrier traps and accelerates carrier transport to luminescence centres independently on the host composition. Apart of that, YAG is more promising as host, because it can be obtained in cheap W/Mo crucibles in contrast to GAGG and other Ga-containing crystals. Due to the synergy between Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} doping of garnets hosts (which mechanisms should be clarified later), we demonstrated that improved combination of light yield and decay time can be achieved in Ce-doped garnets, i.e. larger number of prompt photons can be generated for fast-timing applications. At the same time Sc,Ca codoped YAG:Ce is another promising approach to get fast scintillation crystals with a high light yield that may be grown by a cheap technology from W crucibles.

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